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Digito-Palmar Dermatoglyphics Among the People of Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross Rivier State, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

Dermatoglyphics, the study of epidermal ridge patterns on the fingers and palms, serves as a unique and reliable tool for anthropological and genetic investigation. This research aims to comprehensively analyze and document the patterns, frequencies, and quantitative dermatoglyphics features (ATD angles) among indigenes of Odukpani Local Government Area. The study was carried out among 100 individuals of Odukpani Local Government Area, Cross River State, Nigeria and data collected were using ink and paper methods. The results revealed that loop patterns were the most dominant fingerprint type, with a higher frequency on the left hand (73%) compared to the right hand (68%). Whorl patterns were more prevalent in the right hand (42%) than the left (20%). Gender differences were also observed, with males exhibiting more loops (65%) and females showing a higher prevalence of whorls (31%). Arch patterns were more common in males (17%) than females (11%). Palmprint patterns, however, showed no significant differences between genders, with p-values of 0.700 for the left hand and 0.469 for the right hand. No significant gender differences in palmprint patterns were observed across the sample (p-values > 0.05). The ATD angle was slightly higher in females than in males on both hands. In Right hand, Males have a mean ATD angle of 47.85 ± 1.4 , while females have a slightly higher mean of 49.47 ± 1.5 . In Left hand, Males mean ATD angle is 46.45 ± 1.4 , while females show 47.57 ± 1.6 . The study concluded that fingerprint patterns show significant variation based on both hand dominance and gender, with loops being the most common pattern overall and whorls more frequent in females. In contrast, palmprint patterns showed no significant gender-based differences, suggesting that these traits may be more stable across populations. These findings align with previous

studies, contributing to the broader understanding of dermatoglyphic variability and its genetic underpinnings.

Keywords: Dermatoglyphics, Finger, Patterns

1. INTRODUCTION

Dermatoglyphics, the scientific study of dermal ridge counts and patterns in fingers, palms, and soles, is one field that has attracted great interest across the globe¹⁻². This is especially so for researchers working in relation to genetics, medicine, and anthropology in a bid to explore genetically determined phenotypes, genotypes, and health disease linkages. In this regard, Gutierrez *et al.*³ reported fingerprints to have been used for identification and authentication because of individual peculiarities and uniqueness, and according to Temaj *et al.*⁴ has served as an inexpensive and easily applied tool for estimating the genetic distances between populations. This is because fingerprint and palm print patterns are almost certainly influenced by the interaction of several genes, and the ridge patterns are distinct and unique for every individual, making it widely used in identification⁴. Man's curiosity in the field of dermatoglyphics goes back through centuries around 300 B.C. during the Qin Dynasty, when the Chinese used it as a basis for fortune telling.

About the same period, ancient Indians believed that the presence of ten whorls destined a person to be Chakravarti, meaning "an emperor"⁵. But the systematic study of the whole subject, however, was carried out by Galton around the year 1890. His early interest was in the value of fingerprints for personal and racial groups⁶. It was further elaborated and improved by Sir Edward Richard Henry of Scotland Yard for identifying criminals. It was realized that the uniqueness of fingerprints can serve as valuable indices of human variation, and they are increasingly used in anthropology, medicine, and genetics⁷. Fingerprint is genotypically determined and it is affected by intrauterine environment in the first trimester of pregnancy, though they are characterized by alternating strips of raised frictional ridges and depressed grooves on the fingertips. The characteristic patterns of epidermal ridges are differentiated in their definitive forms during the third and fourth months of fetal life, and they remain unchanged from birth till death.

Dermatoglyphics, the scientific study of epidermal ridge patterns on the skin of the fingers, palms, toes, and soles, has been widely employed in areas such as anthropology, genetics, and evolutionary studies to characterize populations, analyze the nature and origin of human variability, assess population structure, and micro-differentiate among populations. Fingerprints (Figure 1) and Palm prints (Figure 2) are individual-specific and are heritable and plays an important role in human biology research and population studies in medical and genetic studies⁸. The establishments of the epidermal ridge pattern take place from the 10th to 16th weeks of development and these establish the future surface patterns which become well pronounced at the 16th week. Researchers have documented three basic patterns of fingerprint ridges. These basic fingerprint ridge patterns are: Arch (plain and tented), Loop (radial and ulna), and Whorl (plain and others). The arch is a pattern where the ridges enter from one side of the finger, rise in the center forming an arc, and then exit the side of the finger. The loop is a pattern where the ridge enters from one side of a finger forms a curve and tend to exit from the same side from which they enter.

Figure 1. Image displaying the different patterns of finger prints.

In the whorl pattern, ridges form circularly around a central point on the finger. The uniqueness of fingerprint has been attributed to the minutiae. It has been described as the most minute feature in dermatoglyphics and they are reflected in three basic configurations: bifurcations, ending ridges and dots. Their disposition and interrelation within fingerprints are the basic attributes used in forensic investigation, because it has never been discovered that these minutiae are replicated among persons.

Figure 2. Image display of the different categories of palm pattern.

Palmprint is the skin patterns of the inner surface of the human hand from the wrist to the root of the fingers. Palmprints are rich in physical characteristics of skin patterns such as lines, points and textures, which provide stable and distinctive information sufficient for separating an individual from a large population⁹. The friction ridge skin on the palmar surfaces has been studied for more than a century. In the late 1890s through the early 1900s, Inez Whipple researched the ventral surfaces of various monkey species' feet, focusing on the apical pads, ridge patterns, deltas, and other epidermal markings, comparing them to human hands and feet. Harris Wilder, in his *Palm and Sole Studies*, created a system for recording the configuration of various features on the palms and soles into a formula, easily understood and visualized by someone knowing the system. Cummins and Midlo researched pattern frequencies and intensities (number of deltas) in both right and left palms and soles of chimpanzees. Penrose also studied the pattern frequencies of palms and soles, and he and Loesch classified palmar dermatoglyphics, both normal and abnormal.

Research on dermatoglyphics in African populations has revealed significant intra- and inter-population variations, reflecting the continent's rich genetic diversity. Studies have shown that African populations, including those from Nigeria, exhibit distinctive dermatoglyphic patterns that differ from those of other ethnic groups¹⁰. For instance, Ibeachu *et al.*¹¹ reported distinct fingerprint patterns among the Ibibio and Ogoni ethnic groups in southern Nigeria.

The work of Igbigbi *et al.*¹² is part of a broader body of research that underscores the genetic basis for fingerprint pattern variations. Earlier studies indicated that the inheritance of dermatoglyphic traits follows a polygenic model, meaning that multiple genes are involved in the expression of fingerprint patterns¹³. While genetic factors are dominant, environmental influences during fetal development may also contribute to slight variations in fingerprint patterns. The findings have important implications for forensic science, anthropology, and the study of population genetics. Amit *et al.*¹⁴ studied the digital dermatoglyphic patterns of Annang ethnic group in Akwa Ibom State of Nigeria of Nigeria.

The gender-based differences in fingerprint pattern distribution also showed that males exhibited a higher frequency of loop patterns (68%) compared to females (62%), females showed a higher occurrence of whorls (30%) compared to males (26%), arch patterns were slightly more common in males (8%) compared to females (5%). Ujaddughe (2015)¹⁵ studied the dermatoglyphic patterns and sex distribution in Esan ethnic group of Edo state, Nigeria and observed that the loop pattern had the highest frequency (61.7%) followed by whorl (24.9%), arch (12.8%) and double whorl (0.6%). Namouchi (2011)¹⁶ studied the dermatoglyphic trait variations: an intra-Tunisian population analysis observed that the percentage of arches varied from 1.5% to 14.15% for men and from 3.6% to 20.45% for women. The chisquare test revealed high significant differences between the sexes ($\chi^2 = 10.520$; $P = 0.001$) for the frequencies of arches for the little left (the fifth) finger.

The percentage of loops varied from 51.3% to 79.8% for men and from 49.05% to 79.55% for women. The chisquare test revealed significant differences between the sexes for the frequencies of loops for the fourth left fingers ($\chi^2 = 3.908$; $P = 0.048$) and for the first left finger ($\chi^2 = 4.395$; $P = 0.036$). The percentage of whorls varied from 17.2% to 44.45% for men and from 15.45% to 45.9% for women. The difference of the distribution of whorl type between the sexes was statically significant ($\chi^2 = 4.221$; $P = 0.04$) for the fourth left finger. Results of descriptive statistics comparing quantitative digito-palmar dermatoglyphic traits for men and women are presented. The highest number of ridges in both sexes is always on the first finger. The total finger ridge count in men on the left hand (TFRCL) is 69.897 (SD = 23.105) and is

71.931) (SD = 22.859) on the right hand. In women, this ridge count is 67.364 (SD = 25.717) on the left hand and is 68.436 (SD = 22.329) on the right hand. The results of the t-test have not shown significant differences between sexes in finger ridge counts. The use of palm print patterns in biometric security (Kumar & Zhang, 2005)¹⁷. Palm print patterns have been used in anthropology to trace genetic inheritance, population structures, and evolutionary aspects. Furthermore, while fingerprint and iris recognition are the most widely used biometric modalities, palm print recognition is gaining popularity due to its advantages. However, palm print recognition also has its limitations. Factors such as injury, deformities, or excessive hand movements can affect the clarity of the captured image, which may lead to inaccurate identification.

Despite this, advancements in machine learning algorithms have improved the performance of palm print recognition systems under less-than-ideal conditions (Zhang *et al.*, 2010)¹⁸. Recent advances in deep learning and artificial intelligence have transformed the field of palm print recognition. Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs) have been employed to enhance the extraction of features from palm print images, allowing for more accurate and faster identification. Wu *et al.*¹⁹ applied CNNs to palm print recognition and achieved remarkable improvements in identification accuracy compared to traditional methods. Moreover, contactless palm print identification systems have been developed to improve the user experience and hygiene standards in public biometric systems. These systems capture high-resolution palm images without physical contact, reducing wear and tear on the skin, a common issue with fingerprint scanners²⁰.

The study of palm prints is likely to continue evolving with the increasing demand for secure and reliable biometric systems. Future research is expected to focus on improving the accuracy of contactless systems and integrating palm print recognition with other biometric modalities, such as facial recognition, to develop multi-modal systems. Additionally, further exploration into the genetic basis of palm print patterns may provide new insights into their role in human biology and medical diagnostics. Palm print patterns represent a complex and unique form of biometric data, with applications ranging from security systems to medical diagnostics.

The combination of genetic, anthropological, and technological insights into palm prints provides a solid foundation for ongoing research and development in this field. With advancements in AI and machine learning, palm print recognition systems are becoming increasingly accurate, secure, and user-friendly, ensuring their continued relevance in both scientific and practical applications. Despite the extensive research on dermatoglyphics, there is limited information on the variations among homogenous populations in Nigeria, particularly the Odukpani people. Most existing studies have focused on larger ethnic groups, leaving a gap in understanding the dermatoglyphic patterns of smaller, less-studied communities. The current study aims to fill this gap by analyzing the variations in finger and palm dermatoglyphics among the Odukpani people, thereby contributing to the broader body of knowledge on Nigerian and African population genetics.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1. Ethical consideration

This study was approved by the Health Research Ethics Committee of the Ministry of Health Department, Cross River State, Nigeria.

2. 2. Study area

The study was conducted among the people of Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria. It lies between latitude 5°4'52.46"N and longitude 8°20'59.7"E and has an elevation approximately 413ft. It is largely populated by the Efik people. Settlements in Odukpani include Akpap Okoyong, Eki, Eniong Abatim, Ito, Idere, Ukwa Ibom, Creek Town, Inuakpa Okoyong, Okurikang.

2. 3. Collection of sample material

The sample population is drawn from 100 indigenes living in Odukpani Local Government Area of Cross River State.

2. 4. Sampling procedure

Participants from 5 villages were recruited: Okoyong, Eniong Abatim, Creek Town, Okurikang, Akpap Okoyong. Resident of these communities are mostly farmers and fishermen which made them rarely or mostly unavailable at home during the day time except evening hours of the day and these made procuring palm prints and finger prints difficult. Most of the case participants declined to give their palm prints and fingerprints, only 100 participants palm prints gave out samples.

2. 5. Steps in obtaining the prints

The inking method was used to collect digital prints on fingers and palm pattern as suggested by Cummins and Midlo (1961). Briefly, the subjects were asked to clean their hands with soap and water and allowed to dry but with some moisture. Requisite amount of ink was dropped on their hands and was uniformly spread thoroughly on both hands. The completely inked palmar surface of the right hand was then gently pressed on a clean, white bond paper, and it was removed immediately. The same procedure was repeated for the left hand and the ink removed from the subject hands with the aid of about 1% HCl which will neutralize the ink.

The prints were analyzed and classified with the help of a hand lens.

2. 5. Procedure for analysis of prints

2. 5. 1. Finger prints

The interpretation of fingerprint was carried out according to Cummin's method (Cummins et al., 1961) and included the identification of patterns. Qualitative studies were carried out by studying the pattern configuration on fingertips (Whorl, Loop, and Arch). The digital prints of the participants were procured using ink procedure of Cummins et al. (2005).

This method was selected because it is a simple technique, easy-to-use technique with a low cost that gives clear prints and is less time-consuming.

2. 5. 2. Palmprints

Ridge counting in the palm was carried out according to the same principle applied in counting fingerprint ridges. The only difference is ridges of the palm were counted between two digital triradius ATC. Counting was carried out by connecting both triradius with a straight line and the count excludes the ridges-forming triradius. Ridges count between triradial a and

b are referred to as a-b ridge count. ATD angle is formed at the axial Tri radius t, therefore the tad angle was drawn from the digital Tri radius a to axial Tri radius t, and from the axial Tri radius to the digital Tri radius d. A protractor was then used to determine the angle in degrees.

2. 5. 3. Statistical analysis

The data obtained from fingerprint and palm patterns were entered into Microsoft word Excel spread sheet, which were copied into the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) for windows version 27. Qualitative studies on the ATD angle and a-d ridge count were analyzed with t-test while qualitative studies on the pattern configuration on fingertips were well documented and compered between Sexes. The level of significance used was $p < 0.05$.

3. RESULTS

The fingerprint dermatoglyphic variables in all the left hands are displayed in Table 1. The percentage frequency of Loop was significantly larger (73%) in the left-hand participants than in the right hand (68%), frequency in Loop was more prominent in the little left-hand participant. In the right-hand category, the frequency of Whorl in Table 2 was larger (42%) than that of the left hand.

The Relationship between Fingerprint Patterns between left and right hand (Table 3) and The Relationship between Fingerprint Patterns and Gender as shown in Table 4, shows that Loop pattern were more common in males (65%) than in females (56%).

Conversely, females exhibited a higher frequency of Whorls (31%) compared to males (17%). Arches were more frequent in males (17%), while Mixed patterns were rare across both genders. The Relationship between Right and Left Hands as shown in Table 5 highlights that Loops were more frequent on the left hand (63%) compared to the right hand (56%). Whorls showed a higher prevalence on the right hand (30%) compared to the left (20%). Arch patterns had an equal distribution (14%) across both hands. The fingerprint pattern distribution shows a clear dominance of loops across all fingers, with variations in the prevalence of whorls and arches between hands and genders. The gender differences in fingerprint patterns suggest a potential genetic or developmental influence.

Table 1. Distribution of fingerprints pattern of all left fingers among participants.

	PATTERNS	MALE		FEMALE		TOTAL %	
			%		%		
LITTLE FINGER	LOOP	36	49%	37	51%	73	73%
	WHORL	5	28%	13	72%	18	18%
	ARCH	6	67%	3	33%	9	9%
	MIXED	0	0	0	0	0	0%
	TOTAL					100	100%

RING FINGER	LOOP	33	51%	32	49%	65	65%
	WHORL	10	37%	17	63%	27	27%
	ARCH	3	60%	2	40%	5	5%
	MIXED	1	33%	2	67%	3	3%
	TOTAL					100	100%
MIDDLE FINGER	LOOP	32	52%	29	48%	61	61%
	WHORL	3	30%	7	70%	10	10%
	ARCH	10	48%	11	52%	21	21%
	MIXED	2	25%	6	75%	8	8%
	TOTAL					100	100%
INDEX FINGER	LOOP	25	45%	31	55%	56	56%
	WHORL	12	40%	18	60%	30	30%
	ARCH	9	75%	3	25%	12	12%
	MIXED	0	0%	2	100%	2	2%
	TOTAL					100	100%
THUMB	LOOP	29	47%	33	53%	62	62%
	WHORL	4	29%	10	71%	14	14%
	ARCH	14	58%	10	42%	24	24%
	MIXED					0	0%
	TOTAL					100	100%

The analysis of fingerprint patterns across all right-hand fingers revealed that loops were the predominant pattern, followed by whorls, while arches were least frequent. Loops were most common on the little, ring, and middle fingers, whereas the thumb showed the highest frequency of arches.

The index finger displayed nearly equal proportions of loops and whorls, with females contributing more to whorls and males to loops, indicating sexual dimorphism. Overall, females tended to exhibit a higher frequency of whorls, while males showed slightly more loops and arches. These findings align with global dermatoglyphic trends where loops dominate, but also highlight finger-specific and sex-related variations with potential forensic and anthropological significance.

Table 2. Distribution of fingerprints pattern of all right fingers among participants.

	Patterns	Male	%	Female	%	Total	%
LITTLE FINGER	LOOP	37	54%	31	46%	68	68%
	WHORL	8	29%	20	71%	28	28%
	ARCH	2	50%	2	50%	4	4%
	MIXED					0	0%
	TOTAL					100	100%
	RING FINGER	LOOP	29	49%	30	51%	59
WHORL		15	42%	21	58%	36	36%
ARCH		3	60%	2	40%	5	5%
MIXED							
TOTAL						100	100%
MIDDLE FINGER	LOOP	33	50%	33	50%	66	66%
	WHORL	5	29%	12	71%	17	17%
	ARCH	9	53%	8	47%	17	17%
	MIXED					0	0%
	TOTAL					100	100%
INDEX FINGER	LOOP	26	62%	16	38%	42	42%
	WHORL	11	27%	30	73%	41	41%
	ARCH	9	60%	6	40%	15	15%
	MIXED	1	50%	1	50%	2	2%
	TOTAL					100	100%
THUMB	LOOP	24	51%	23	49%	47	47%
	WHORL	8	31%	18	69%	26	26%
	ARCH	15	56%	12	44%	27	27%
	MIXED					0	0%
	TOTAL					100	100%

The study below (Table 3) reveals that loops are the most frequent fingerprint pattern overall, followed by whorls and arches, with mixed patterns being rare. Loops are more dominant on the left hand, while whorls occur more on the right, indicating bilateral asymmetry. Arches are equally distributed across both hands, showing stability. These results not only align with global dermatoglyphic trends but also underscore subtle left-right variations that may have forensic and anthropological relevance.

Table 3. Relationship of fingerprints patterns between left and right hand.

	Loop	%	Whorl	%	Arches	%	Mixed	%	Total	%
Left	317	63%	99	20%	71	14%	13	3%	500	100%
Right	282	56%	148	30%	68	14%	2	0%	500	100%
Total	599	60%	247	25%	139	14%	15	2%	1000	100%

Table 4 shows that loops were the most common fingerprint pattern in both sexes, but they occurred more frequently in males (63–66%) than in females (50–61%). In contrast, whorls were more prevalent among females (24–38%) compared to males (15–20%), while arches were slightly more common in males (16–18%) than in females (11%).

Mixed patterns were rare overall but were higher in females (up to 4%) than in males (1%). These findings confirm the dominance of loops across both sexes but also highlight clear sexual dimorphism, with males tending toward loops and arches, while females displayed a greater proportion of whorls and mixed patterns.

Such variations have important forensic and anthropological implications, particularly in sex differentiation and population characterization.

Table 4. Relationship between Gender and fingerprints patterns in right and left hand.

Hand	Gender	Loop	%	Whorl	%	Arches	%	Mixed	%	Total	%
Right Hand	Male	149	63%	47	20%	38	16%	1	0%	235	100%
	Female	133	50%	101	38%	30	11%	1	0%	265	100%
	Total	282	56%	148	30%	68	14%	2	0%	500	100%
Left Hand	Male	155	66%	34	15%	42	18%	3	1%	234	100%
	Female	162	61%	65	24%	29	11%	10	4%	266	100%
	Total	317	63%	99	20%	71	14%	13	3%	500	100%

Palmprint analysis

The analysis of palmprint categories (CAT2, CAT4, CAT5) as shown in Table 5, shows no significant gender-based differences in either hand, with p-values greater than 0.05. This shows that the distribution of palmprint patterns is not significantly influenced by gender. The result in Table 7 Shows *Left ATD*: The p-value of 0.178 indicates no significant difference between genders in the left hand. *Right ATD*: The p-value of 0.052 is close to the significance threshold, indicating a possible gender difference in the right hand. *Left and Right Palm Patterns*: The p-values of 0.700 and 0.469 respectively, indicate no significant gender difference in palmprint patterns for both hands.

Table 5. Relationship between palmprints and Gender.

Hand	Category	Male	Female	Total	Test stat
Left Hand	CAT2	14	18	32	DF=3 P-VALUE = 0.700
	CAT4	9	9	18	
	CAT5	24	26	50	
	Total	47	53	100	
Right Hand	CAT2	9	13	22	DF = 3 P-VALUE = 0.469
	CAT4	10	12	22	
	CAT5	28	28	56	
	Total	47	53	100	

4. DISCUSSION

In this study, the dominant fingerprint pattern across both hands was the loop, with a frequency of (73%) in the left hand and (68%) in the right hand. This finding is consistent with previous research, which has widely established loops as the most common fingerprint pattern globally²¹. The prevalence of loops in the little finger of the left hand (73%) further supports this trend, reflecting the genetic stability of loop patterns in human populations. However, the increased frequency of whorls in the right hand (42%) compared to the left (20%) suggests a potential hand-specific asymmetry in the development of fingerprint patterns. Such asymmetry has been reported in various studies²² which argues that genetic factors combined with slight environmental influences during fetal development may lead to differences between hands. The greater frequency of whorls on the right hand observed in this study aligns with findings from research on other populations, which also noted higher whorl patterns in dominant hands²³.

The relationship between gender and fingerprint patterns observed in this study aligns with the broader literature on dermatoglyphics. Males exhibited a higher frequency of loops (65%) compared to females (56%), while females had a significantly higher frequency of

whorls (31%) compared to males (17%). These findings are consistent with those of previous studies, which have often shown that loops are more common in males, while females tend to have a higher prevalence of whorls²⁴. This gender-based difference could be attributed to the influence of sex-linked genetic factors that govern the development of dermatoglyphic traits²⁵.

Table 6. Mean ATD angle of Left and Right Hand.

		Males	Females
Mean ATD angle	Right hand	47.85±1.4	49.47±1.5
Mean ATD angle	Left hand	46.45±1.4	47.57±1.6

ATD: Axial tri-radius around D

The ATD angle was slightly higher in females than in males on both hands (Table 6). In Right hand, Males have a mean ATD angle of 47.85±1.4, while females have a slightly higher mean of 49.47±1.5. In Left hand, Males mean ATD angle is 46.45±1.4, while females show 47.57±1.6. This indicates a small but consistent gender-based difference in ATD angle, with females generally having a wider angle.

Table 7. Independent Sample Test.

	Sig. (2-tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference	
				Lower	Upper
LEFT ATD	0.178	-1.1192	0.8248	-2.7560	0.5175
RIGHT ATD	0.052	-1.6206	0.8234	-3.2547	0.0134
LEFT PALM PATTERNS	0.700	0.104	0.268	-0.429	0.636
RIGHT PALM PATTERNS	0.469	0.175	0.241	-0.303	0.653

The Independent Sample Test revealed that there is no significant difference in the left-hand ATD patterns between males and females, as indicated by the p-value of 0.178. The right-hand ATD patterns approached significance (p-value of 0.052), suggesting a potential but weak gender effect. No significant differences were found for left and right palm print patterns between genders, with p-values of 0.700 and 0.469, respectively.

Interestingly, arches were slightly more frequent in males (17%) than in females (11%), which also concurs with previous research indicating a modest male advantage in arch frequency

However, mixed fingerprint patterns were rare across both genders in this study, which contrasts with some studies that have found more variability in mixed patterns, especially in females²⁶. This could be due to population-specific genetic differences or the limited sample size of the present study. The observed decrease in loop patterns from the left hand (63%) to the right hand (56%) suggests a potential variation in the genetic or environmental factors that influence fingerprint development. Asymmetry between hands in dermatoglyphic patterns has been a subject of interest in numerous studies. For example, Meier²⁷ noted that such asymmetry could reflect subtle developmental variations, including differences in blood flow or physical stress during intrauterine development. The increase in whorl patterns on the right hand (30%) compared to the left (20%) further supports the idea of hand asymmetry, which may be influenced by genetic predisposition or handedness²⁸.

In addition, the relatively stable distribution of arch patterns between the left (14%) and right (14%) hands indicates that certain fingerprint patterns may be less affected by these factors. This finding supports the theory that while loops and whorls may be influenced by hand dominance, arches tend to show less variability across hands²⁹. The analysis of palmprint patterns in this study revealed no significant gender-based differences, as evidenced by p-values greater than 0.05 for both hands.

This aligns with the findings of Gutiérrez-Redomero et al.³⁰ who reported similar results in their investigation of palmprint patterns, concluding that palmprint traits tend to be more stable and less influenced by gender compared to fingerprint patterns. The lack of significant gender differences in palmprint patterns in this study reinforces the view that, unlike fingerprints, palmprint features are more uniform across different demographic groups. However, the near-significant p-value (0.052) observed in the right-hand palmprint analysis may suggest a slight trend toward gender-based differences in palmprints. Similar borderline results have been reported in studies by Amrouni et al.³¹ who found minor, though not statistically significant, differences in palmprint patterns between genders in specific populations. The findings of this study can be compared with the work of Igbigbi *et al.*¹², who also examined fingerprint patterns among Nigerian populations. In their study, the Ibibio and Ogoni ethnic groups showed distinct differences in fingerprint patterns, with the Ibibio exhibiting a higher frequency of loops and the Ogoni showing a greater prevalence of whorls.

This supports the notion that ethnic and population-specific genetic factors play a significant role in shaping dermatoglyphic patterns. While this study focused more on gender differences, the overall dominance of loop patterns and the variability in whorl patterns are consistent with Igbigbi *et al.* findings¹².

Additionally, Igbigbi *et al.*¹² conducted a similar study in India, where they also observed gender-based differences in fingerprint patterns, with loops being more common in males and whorls more frequent in females. The comparison between left and right hands in their study mirrored the results of the present research, showing a higher prevalence of whorls on the right hand. These consistent trends across different populations further emphasize the role of genetic and developmental factors in dermatoglyphic variation. The fingerprint pattern distribution in this study shows clear gender differences, with males displaying more loops and females more whorls, while arch patterns remain relatively stable across both genders. The asymmetry between the left and right hands, with loops more frequent in the left hand and whorls more common in the right hand, may indicate the influence of both genetic and environmental factors during development. In contrast, palmprint patterns show no significant gender differences, suggesting that they may be more genetically conserved compared to fingerprints.

The results of this study are consistent with other dermatoglyphic research, supporting the role of genetics in shaping fingerprint patterns, with slight modifications due to hand dominance and environmental factors.

In summary, Loop patterns were dominant in both hands across all fingers, more so in males than females. Whorl patterns were more frequent in females, especially in the right hand. Arch patterns showed minimal variation between hands and genders, though slightly more common in males. Mixed patterns were rare, occurring in only a few cases. Males exhibited a higher percentage of loop patterns, while females had a significantly higher percentage of whorls. Arches were distributed similarly between genders, with a slightly higher frequency among males. The right hand of females had a notably higher percentage of whorls compared to males, while males had more loops in both hands. No significant gender difference was found in palmprint patterns. The distribution of categories (CAT2, CAT4, CAT5) was relatively uniform across genders. The independent sample test revealed no significant difference between left-hand ATD patterns between genders, while right-hand ATC patterns showed a borderline significance. Palmprint patterns showed no significant gender influence

5. CONCLUSION

This study on the digito-palmar dermatoglyphics among the people of Odukpani Local Government Area in Cross River State reveals that loop patterns are the most prevalent dermatoglyphic feature in the studied population, with notable gender-based variations: males exhibit a higher percentage of loops, while females display a significantly higher occurrence of whorls. These findings offer insights into the dermatoglyphic characteristics of this population and can be applied to forensic science for identifying individuals, where the noted gender differences could assist in narrowing down suspects. Furthermore, as dermatoglyphics may offer insights into genetic predispositions to certain diseases, these results warrant investigation into the possible genetic or environmental factors contributing to the observed patterns.

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